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Challenging the Unchallenged. A Critical Examination and Refutation of Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction has long been regarded as a cornerstone of classical logic, philosophy and of science as such. It asserts that contradictory propositions, properties, events et cetera cannot both be true at the same time and in the same sense. This principle has underpinned Western philosophical reasoning since thousands of years.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This article embarks on a critical journey to reevaluate Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction, subjecting it to rigorous scrutiny within the context of modern philosophy and science. We examine its implications under extreme conditions, where Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction encounters challenges, notably in the realm of Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity.

RESULTS:

Our investigation reveals that under certain extraordinary circumstances, particularly those involving high speeds and relativistic physics, Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction encounters tensions with empirical observations and theoretical developments. Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction, while treated as invaluable in many contexts, may not consistently align with the complex realities of the real world.

CONCLUSION:

While Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction still governs classical logic, our exploration calls for a nuanced perspective. We advocate for an appreciation of the limits of Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction in addressing phenomena at the edges of human understanding, where empirical evidence and scientific theories challenge this traditional philosophical axiom. Our findings invite a broader dialogue about the dynamic interplay between logic, science, and philosophy in our pursuit of knowledge and to consider again the unity of nature as the foundation of the unity of science.

Keywords:

Aristotle; Law Of Contradiction; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

The Law of Contradiction is one of the fundamental principles of classical logic and represents a significant historical and philosophical milestone in the development of classical logic, and remains a central principle in the field of logic and philosophy to this day. The Law of Contradiction is attributed to the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle, who lived from 384 to 322 before current era (BCE). Aristotle's contributions to logic and philosophy laid the groundwork for much of Western philosophical thought. However, the terms Law of Contradiction and Law of Non-Contradiction are often used interchangeably and generally referred to the same fundamental principle in logic. Nonetheless, it's essential to clarify the meaning of these two different notions in order to avoid confusion. In the search for clarity of the central notion of contradiction, it is perhaps highly inappropriate that the central principle at issue goes under these two apparently contradictory names. However, a contradiction is not the same as a non-contradiction. Therefore, a Law of Contradiction cannot be the same as the Law of Non-Contradiction. The Law of Non-Contradiction focuses on the negation or absence of a contradiction, and is often treated only as a specific expression of the law of contradiction. In other words, the clarification of such a simple and central notion like contradiction is far from being simple. On this view, we are left with the issue, what is a contradiction? The notion of contradiction has been discussed by various authors. Aristotle's discussion of the principle of contradiction can be found for example in *De Interpretatione*, in *Posterior Analytics I et cetera*. Nonetheless, the most famous and main discussion of Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction occurs in *Metaphysics IV (Gamma)* 3–6, especially 4 (see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#)).

“... it is impossible for anything at the same time to be and not to be
... this is the most indisputable of all principles. ”
(see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340))

In philosophy and general language, an attribute is considered more or less as a property or characteristic belonging to something else, typically an object, entity, or subject et cetera. The Law of Contradiction is valid for the whole something but for the properties of something too. In *Metaphysics IV (Gamma)*, Aristotle defines the most certain of all principles again as follows:

“Evidently ... a principle is the most certain of all ... It is, that the same attribute cannot at the same time belong and not belong to the same subject in the same respect ... ”
(see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 3 1005b19–23* (pdf p. 82/340))

Law of Contradiction and bivalent logic

The principle of contradiction is an indispensable foundation in scientific inquiry, and we cannot do without while Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction can be seen as a form of definition *ex negativo*, which is a type of definition that describes something by stating what it is not. Can this

be done in the positive way? Besides all, Aristotle is talking about the relationship between “... to be **and** not to be ... ”at the same time t (see Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)). Aristotle unfortunately does not specify in this matter whether he is considering the relationship between something and its own other, its own negation, from the standpoint of the co-moving or internal observer (O) or from the standpoint of the stationary or external observer (R). This small yet significant difference is of great importance. At the end, the fundamental question is, indeed, can something be and not be at the same time? In formal logic, a conjunction (symbolized by $\wedge$) represents a logical operation. Aristotle is combining to be, (*symbolized by* (X_{Rt})) with not to be (*symbolized by* $\neg(X_{Rt})$) while their internal relationship is regulated by the logical operation conjunction in the sense “... to be **and** not to be ... ”(see Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)). Conjunction itself is an operation or may be even a natural process that connects especially those which are different. However, those which are different can be independent of each other even if conjugated. Thus far, the process of conjunction does not determine any kind of dependence between those which are different. Nonetheless, Aristotle compels us to adopt a one-sided and overly dogmatic perspective on the relationship between “... to be **and** not to be ... ”(see Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)). Why should the subsequent relationships between “... to be **and** not to be ... ”such as if “... to be ... ”, then “... not to be ... ”or without “... to be ... ”, no “... not to be ... ”or neither “... to be ... ”, nor “... not to be ... ”or either “... to be ... ”, or “... not to be ... ”and so on, all existing at the same time, not be considered? The relationship between “... to be ... ”, and “... not to be ... ”appears to us as too complex to be unilaterally reduced, in the Aristotelian sense, to a mere conjugation between “... to be ... ”, and “... not to be ... ”. Be that as it may, Aristotle himself insists, in his understanding of the relationship between “... to be ... ”, and “... not to be ... ”, as a one-sided relationship in the sense of a conjugation. However, it is still a conjunction between those which are different “... **at the same time** ... ”(see Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)). Such a conjunction describes primarily a kind of coincidence between those which are different “... **at the same time** ... ”(see Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)) and not dependence. Coincidence refers to circumstances where something occurs together in time or space with something other, including its own other, but their occurrence is not necessarily related or dependent on each other. Coincidence in classical logic is very well described by conjunction. A more detailed discussion of the identity and the difference between coincidence and conjunction may be found somewhere else in secondary literature. Thus far, at a certain point or period in (space-) time t

$$(X_{Rt}) = (X_{Rt}) \quad (1)$$

is identical with itself. However, at the same point or period in (space-) time t , the other of something, the negation of something,

$$\neg(X_{Rt}) = \neg(X_{Rt}) \quad (2)$$

is identical with itself too. Thus far, both which are different are identical too. However, is such a view really coherent? Nonetheless, why should and how can the identity of something be worth less than the identity of its own other and vice versa? Combining these both identities by conjunction, we obtain

$$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = ((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) \quad (3)$$

Equation 3 tell us only that something and its own other are conjugated but not whether there is any interaction or dependence between both. Table 1 provide us with an overview of the equation 3 under

the assumption of independence between (X_{Rt}) and its own other, denoted by $\neg(X_{Rt})$. As can be seen, under conditions of classical logic, conjunction is true only when both of the individual parts are true, otherwise not.

Table 1. Law of Contradiction and independence

At the same time t	(X_{Rt})	$\neg(X_{Rt})$	$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$
1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0
3	0	1	0
4	0	0	0
...	...	...	...

Conjunction in classical logic or as a natural process has the potential to create something new by combining two or more other. However, as demonstrated by table 1, it is not the conjugation which creates a contradiction. It is especially the understanding of the relationship between something and its own other which is important in this context (see also table 2).

Table 2. The Law of Contradiction and independence

	$\neg(X_{Rt})$		
	1	0	
(X_{Rt})	1	0	1
	0	0	0
	1	0	1

Nonetheless, Aristotle himself insists that the relationship between “... to be ...”, and “... not to be ...” according to his understanding is determined “... **at the same time** ...” (see Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10 (pdf p. 83/340)) only in a very specific manner. We must accept that either “... to be ...” or “... not to be ...” is true, but not both simultaneously. Therefore, if “... to be ...” exists, then “... not to be ...” does not exist, it is not given, there is only “... to be ...” and vice versa. Aristotle’s understanding of the Law of Contradiction is illustrated by table 3.

Aristotle’s understanding of the Law of Contradiction is based on an oversimplification of the relationship between something and its own negation, and implies hasty conclusions. Aristotle unfairly restricts the range of our possibilities with respect to something and its own other by presenting **only two extreme options** (see table 1), either something or its own other, its own negation, thus preventing a thorough exploration of a very complex issue. In the end, who ultimately benefits from such an approach? Aristotle describes the relationship between something and its own other, its own negation as if there are only two mutually exclusive options or possibilities when, in reality, there are more al-

Table 3. Aristotle and the Law of Contradiction

At the same			
time	(X_{Rt})	$\neg(X_{Rt})$	$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$
t			
1	1	0	0
2	1	0	0
3	0	1	0
4	0	1	0
...	...	...	...

ternatives to consider. By using such a starting point of his understanding of the Law of Contradiction in his arguments, Aristotle employs an argumentative shortcut that is neither permissible nor logically warranted. *Ipsa facto*, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction is based on the fallacy of the excluded middle, also known as the false dilemma or either/or fallacy. At the end, Aristotle's goal is to undermine the depth and richness of any inquiry on the Law of Contradiction.

It is worth noting with particular consideration that Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction is plagued by various inadequacies. Considering table 1 and the point in time $t = 4$, neither something nor its own other is given, both are just not existing. However, such a case is not possible according to Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction. According to Aristotle (see table 3) either something is existing or its negation is existing. As a consequence, one of both must exist at a certain time t . It is not possible that both do not exist at this time t , which constitutes an extreme drawback and perhaps a systematic flaw in Aristotle's perspective on the Law of Contradiction (see table 4).

Table 4. Aristotle and the Law of Contradiction

		$\neg(X_{Rt})$		
		1	0	
(X_{Rt})	1	0	1	1
	0	1	0	1
		1	1	2

Furthermore, the sample space of such an approach ends up at 2 (see table 4). In order to normalize this situation, the value of something and its own other need to be changed to 1/2 (see table 5), which is per definition neither possible nor allowed.

At the end, Aristotle is contradicting himself on the Law of Contradiction. One consequence of Aristotle's approach to the law of Contradiction is that if something does exist, its own negation does

Table 5. Aristotle and the Law of Contradiction

		$\neg(X_{Rt})$		
		1	0	
(X_{Rt})	1	0	1/2	1/2
	0	1/2	0	1/2
		1/2	1/2	1

not exist. For instance, suppose something indicates a small stone on our earth, while its own negation is given by all but this small stone that is the rest of our world including the rest of our universe. Thus far, if such a small stone does exist, then the rest of our world including the rest of our universe does not exist, because both cannot exist at the same time. Such an understanding of the relationship between something and its own other is without any sense and contradicts our everyday experience. Unfortunately, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction does not take into account that something itself may not be given as an absolute value but might exist only gradually and to a limited degree. In this case, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction breaks down because it recognizes only extremes, either to be (+1) or not to be (+0) as such and nothing between. This leads to various philosophical and scientific issues.

Simple Real-World Counter-Example to Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction

The use of counterexamples in gaining knowledge is a valuable tool, as it helps to challenge and refine existing theories, hypotheses et cetera. Counterexamples can expose limitations or even flaws in existing theories and hypotheses, promoting critical thinking and progress. However, counterexamples might not always represent the broader truth, with the consequence that relying solely on counterexamples can be misleading if not used judiciously. With this in mind, the following counterexample should be able to illustrate the fundamental challenges with Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction. Thus far, let us confront Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction with every day reality, what does real-life or objective reality as such tell us about Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction?

A young boy is looking at a plate of **10 apples** on the table in front of him and thinks about what to do. His mother, a professor of logic and philosophy, notices this and said. Son, please let me help you,

“... it is impossible for you at the same time
to eat all 10 apples
and
not to eat all 10 apples
... this is the most indisputable of all principles. ”

(I refer you on this issue to [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10 \(pdf p. 83/340\)](#))

and the mother continues. Therefore, son, “either you do eat all 10 apples or you do not eat all 10 apples, both actions are not possible at the same time.” Mother’s comment causes the young boy to ponder. Mother, you know that the more apples I eat, the more stomachaches I have, the young boy said. The young boy unexpectedly finds himself under pressure and asks his mother again with some concern:

Mother, I have 10 apples,

if I eat 1 apple, then at the same time I do not eat 9 apples,

if I eat 2 apples, then at the same time I do not eat 8 apples,

if I eat 5 apples, then at the same time I do not eat 5 apples,

and so forth.

In other words, as soon as I have chosen “not to eat 5 apples,” I have equally chosen to eat 5 apples.

Mother,

why am I not allowed at the same time to eat 5 apples and not eat 5 apples?

The mother, still very patient and full of understanding, explains the laws of nature and life to her son with all necessary logical clarity. Son,

“... it is impossible for you at the same time
to eat 5 apples
and
not to eat 5 apples
... this is the most indisputable of all principles. ”

(Son, I must refer you again on this issue to the great [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 4* 1008b8–10 (pdf p. 83/340))

One gets the impression that the son is not entirely convinced by the mother’s arguments.

Mother, the little boy replied a little unsurely, I’m not sure if I really understand you.

If I eat 5 apples, which corresponds to the Aristotelian “to be”, at the same time, I do not eat 10 apples - 5 apples = 5 apples, which is the negation of 5 apples and which corresponds to Aristotle’s “not to be”.

In other words, it is not impossible at the same time to eat 5 apples and not to eat 5 apples.

The relationship between human experience and scientific theories and hypotheses is not free of tension. However, experiments or human experience has the potential to correct erroneous human

thinking, scientific theories and hypotheses. Aristotle himself, even in his time, had the opportunity and knew about the possibility to confront his own erroneous or at least questionable thinking with reality, to test his ideas against the empirical world. In his otherworldly attacks on Heraclitus, Aristotle implies that he knew about the possibility of how and the necessity of confronting one's own thinking with reality. Aristotle is writing:

“... it is impossible to step twice into the same river ... ”

(Heraclitus, cited according to [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 5 1010a 27–28* (pdf p. 93/340))

What could this mean? Is it wrong? Why is it wrong? What is the value of such a stance, et cetera? However, Aristotle did not feel compelled to consider any confrontation of his own thinking with reality. One can't help but get the impression that Aristotle himself was irrevocably convinced in his own stance, and that Aristotle has been possibly the very first victim of a long series of further victims of his own anti-realistic and erroneous principles. In classical logic, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction is still treated as valid. In particular, we can no longer ignore the fact that when applied to real-world scenarios, such as the previous example of 10 apples, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction breaks down.

In order to salvage Aristotle's inherently contradictory understanding of the Law of Contradiction, there have indeed been concerted efforts within the realm of philosophical inquiry to separate Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction from the real world or its original ontological (related to the nature of being) source and to treat this issue primarily as an epistemic topic (related to knowledge) or as a simple rule of logic. However, as an ontological principle, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction asserts that “contradiction is not possible and, therefore, cannot exist in reality” (see [Massie, 2022](#)). In brief, the evidence of the tension between Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction and the ambiguities of human experience, as provided by the 10 apples counterexample, becomes more and more apparent. When confronted with real-world scenarios, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction is of none or of very limited epistemological value.

In toto, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction leaves out and forbids reasonable options and unjustifiably forces us to choose between extremes, a more balanced choice or option is prohibited by Aristotle. However, the reality in this matter is quite different, as demonstrated by the counterexample just before. In other words, Aristotle's approach to the Law of Contradiction is based on a false dilemma fallacy or either/or fallacy. In complete contrast to Aristotle, objective reality every day anew provide us with reliable evidence that something and its own negation, its own other, is given at the same time.

Nonetheless, the significant issues with Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction does not end here in any way. Aristotle insists that the relationship between “... to be ... ” and “... not to be ... ” is given “... **at the same time** ... ” (see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)) although Aristotle remains quite reserved or even completely silent on his own concept of simultaneity. Nonetheless, the concept of simultaneity or of “... **at the same time** ... ” (see [Aristotle,](#)

384-322 B.C.E., *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340)) according to Aristotle can vary depending on the relative motion of observers (see [Einstein, 1905](#)). Simultaneity is relative; the relationship between “... **to be** ... ”(see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10 \(pdf p. 83/340\)\) and “... **not to be** ... ”\(see \[Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10 \\(pdf p. 83/340\\)\\) that appear simultaneous to Aristotle may not appear so to another who is in relative motion to these entities. The question is, does this change the essence of Aristotle’s understanding of the Law Contradiction in any way, is Aristotle’s understanding of the Law Contradiction at the end relative? In other words, is it only within a specific observer’s reference frame, that something and its negation cannot both be true at the same moment \\(see \\[Barukčić, 2019\\]\\(#\\)\\), but not in general? It is more than evident that Aristotle’s view of the Law of Contradiction is dogmatic, overly one-sided, and marked by significant deficiencies and not quite aligning with the essence and nature of the Law of Contradiction. Can we, and should we, ultimately strive to improve our understanding of the Law of Contradiction?\]\(#\)](#)

Before we attempt to delve deeper into issues like these, let us emphasize that the Law of Contradiction should clearly also indicate a contradiction, while the Law of Non-Contradiction should clearly also indicate a non-contradiction. Formally and in contrast to Aristotle’s understanding, the coincidence of something and its own negation is theoretically neither forbidden nor impossible. Again, let us consider that the equation

$$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) \quad (4)$$

is just a formal description of the coincidence of something and its own other at the same time t , but does not say anything about the character of the internal relationship between something and its own negation and whether there is any inherent relationship occurring or existent simultaneously between them. Foremost, (X_{Rt}) represents something, which (under conditions of classical logic) can be either true ($=+1$) or false ($=+0$). In the same sense, $(\neg(X_{Rt}))$ represents the negation of something, which (under conditions of classical logic) itself can be either true ($=+1$) or false ($=+0$). Equation 4 describes only the coincidence of something and its own negation, but does not say anything about their internal relationship. Theoretically, something and its own other can exist independently of each other, too. In general, under conditions of classical logic, there might exist circumstances, where

$$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = +0 \quad (5)$$

is given. Under these conditions, the left side of equation 5 is equal with $+0$. We obtain,

$$+0 = +1 - 1 = +1 - 1 = +0 \quad (6)$$

In other words, equation 5 does not express any kind of contradiction, it is an expression of the Law of Non-Contradiction or of the identity law. We obtain

$$+1 = +1 \quad (7)$$

Equation 5 can be expressed in the negative as

$$+1 - ((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = +1 - 0 = +1 \quad (8)$$

In general, in terms of classical logic, **the Law of Non-Contradiction** or the identity law, can be expressed too as

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = -0 = +1 \quad (9)$$

However, the relationship between something and its own other, $((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$, can be determined by a contradiction too. This is given under conditions of classical logic where

$$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = +1 \quad (10)$$

or in the negative, wehre

$$1 - ((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = +1 - 1 = +0 \quad (11)$$

In general, in terms of classical logic, **the Law of Contradiction** can be expressed something as

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = \neg 1 = +0 \quad (12)$$

Furthermore, Aristotle is using the notion impossible without defining the same to a necessary extent. In this context, the terms *impossible* and *not possible* are often used interchangeably in everyday language to convey the fact that something cannot occur or be achieved. At the end, both notions indicate that an event et cetera cannot occur. Nonetheless, these terms can carry nuanced distinctions in the sense that the extent to which something cannot occur might be different. The notion *not possible* is all but possible, and depends in this way on the extent to which something is possible. In point of fact, something which is impossible is completely the other of possible, any possible is no longer given. Ultimately, Aristotle introduces equally a concept of impossibility by stating that it is impossible for something to both be and not be simultaneously and demanding that being both itself, and it's opposite simultaneously is impossible. If we closely follow Aristotle, we understand what is impossible. However, the question of what is possible in the relationship between opposites remains fundamentally unanswered by Aristotle. Is there anything which is possible between opposites? Are there no opposites in our world? Do Aristotle's explanations and insights suffice to fully explain the fundamental relationships between opposites?

Law of Contradiction and probability theory

Probability theory has its own axioms and principles that govern how probabilities are assigned to events and how probabilistic reasoning is conducted. However, Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction which is not explicitly formulated within probability theory is still relevant when applying probability theory. In probability theory, an event is considered impossible when its probability of occurring is equal to zero $p(X_{Rt}) = 0$. This means that, under the given circumstances and within the defined sample space, the event cannot occur, and there is no chance or possibility of it happening. To bring it to the point, under circumstances where the probability assigned to an event is explicitly zero, such an event is impossible by definition. For instance, the probability of drawing a blue card from a deck of cards that contains only red cards would be zero. In other words, if the sample space, which includes all possible outcomes of an experiment or event, does not include the specific outcome associated with the event, then that event is impossible per definition or straightforward, if the event's outcome cannot occur within the defined sample space, it is impossible. To recall, events with a probability of zero are guaranteed not to occur in the given context and are, therefore, considered impossible. However, every single event is at least mutually exclusive with itself and is at the same time in a state of super-position of at least two sides which exist simultaneously. Therefore, if the probability that an event X_{Rt} will occur is $p(X_{Rt}) = 0$ then the probability that the same event X_{Rt} will not occur is

$p(\underline{X}_{Rt}) = 1 - p(X_{Rt}) = +1$. Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction expressed in terms of probability theory could take the form

$$(p(X_{Rt}) \times (1 - p(X_{Rt}))) = +0 \quad (13)$$

As long as we operate with probabilities like either $p(X_{Rt}) = +0$ or $p(X_{Rt}) = +1$, we find ourselves in the realm of classical logic or probability theory itself has transitioned into classical logic. However, in real life, probabilities are not always identical either to $p(X_{Rt}) = +0$ or to $p(X_{Rt}) = +1$. Probabilities usually fall somewhere in between. In other words, on the right side of the equation 13, we obtain a value which is different from zero. It is

$$(p(X_{Rt}) \times (1 - p(X_{Rt}))) = (p(X_{Rt}) \times (1 - p(X_{Rt}))) \quad (14)$$

Multiplying equation 14 by $(X_{Rt}) \times (X_{Rt})$ we obtain

$$(X_{Rt}) \times (X_{Rt}) \times (p(X_{Rt}) \times (1 - p(X_{Rt}))) = (X_{Rt}) \times (X_{Rt}) \times (p(X_{Rt}) \times (1 - p(X_{Rt}))) \quad (15)$$

The variance, denoted by $\sigma(X_{Rt})^2$, is a measure of the inner contradiction between something and its own other. It is

$$(X_{Rt}) \times (p(X_{Rt}) \times (X_{Rt}) \times (1 - p(X_{Rt}))) = E(X_{Rt}) \times E(\underline{X}_{Rt}) = \sigma(X_{Rt})^2 \quad (16)$$

How can we know that we mean to know? In the realm of quantum mechanics, where particles can exist in super-positions of states, there is a notion that classical logic and the Law of Contradiction might not fully apply at the quantum level. Some physicists argue that quantum events may not adhere to classical logical principles. However, as seen before, under conditions where the variance of an event (see Barukčić, 2021) is $\sigma(X_{Rt})^2 = +0$ we reached the state of pure classical logic and (Aristotle's understanding of) the Law of Contradiction applies as known. Nonetheless, as soon as the variance of an event is $\sigma(X_{Rt})^2 > +0$ we have provided the proof that something and its own other, its own opposite, are existing simultaneously, and the greater the variance, the greater the internal contradiction inherent in every such event, the greater the struggle within such an event or entity. In other words, the variance as such appears to be one possible and adequate probabilistic formulation of the Law of Contradiction, quantum mechanics included. In probability theory, contradictory sides of events (sides that are both true and false simultaneously) are considered possible as soon as their probability is different from zero.

Historically, while Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction was highly respected, his approach to the Law of Contradiction was also subjected to intense scrutiny and debate as too simplistic to capture all the complexities of objective reality. Equation 16 has been able to demonstrate why. It is therefore not surprising to us that critiques of Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction have arisen over the centuries, and while it is a foundational principle in classical logic, some philosophers and logicians have raised objections or alternative viewpoints and explored the boundaries of Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction, examining whether there were any exceptions or cases where contradictions might be allowed. As an example, Jan Łukasiewicz, a Polish logician and philosopher who lived from 1878 to 1956, made significant contributions to modern logic, including work related to the Law of Contradiction (see Łukasiewicz, 1910; Łukasiewicz and Wedin, 1971)

and non-classical logics. While Łukasiewicz was a proponent of classical logic, he was also one of the first who pioneered alternative systems of logic and who explored alternative logics that extended or modified classical logic to accommodate a broader range of truth values, particularly three-valued and many-valued logics. Meanwhile, there are trials (para-consistent logics, dialectical logics et cetera), which are designed to handle contradictions in a controlled and systematic way.

We must consider the theoretical possibility that the probability of an event can be viewed as the truth value of the event within the context of multi-valued or dialectical logic. In conventional classical logic, an event is typically seen as either true (with a probability of 1) or false (with a probability of 0). However, in real-world scenarios, probabilities often exist along a spectrum, reflecting a degree of uncertainty. This departure from the binary true-false dichotomy raises questions about how we represent and reason with probabilities. Within the framework of multi-valued or dialectical logic, we can explore the idea that probabilities can take on values between 0 and 1, representing various degrees of truth or validity. This perspective acknowledges the inherent uncertainty and complexity of real-world phenomena, where events may have a partial truth value. It allows us to capture the nuances of uncertain knowledge and embrace the idea that events can be 'more true' or 'less true' rather than strictly either true or false. In this view, the probability of an event becomes a measure of its plausibility or likelihood, and logical reasoning can accommodate a spectrum of possibilities. Such an approach offers a richer and more flexible way to model and understand the uncertain nature of reality, where events are not confined to a binary state but can exhibit varying degrees of truth, reflecting the intricacies of the world we observe. In this publication, we intend to subject Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction to a closer examination.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Definitions

Providing clear and precise meanings for concepts, terms, and phenomena is one of the main task of definitions. Definitions enable an effective communication between scientist and might contribute to consistency in scientific research. Without well-defined notions, it becomes challenging to convey knowledge, make accurate observations, or draw meaningful conclusions. Are definitions inherently true and do the same remain beyond the scope of scientific scrutiny?

2.1.1. The Law of Non-Contradiction

In today's science, the Law of Non-Contradiction is a fundamental principle that asserts the impossibility of a something, denoted by X_{Rt} , and its own negation, denoted by $\neg X_{Rt}$, being simultaneously at the same (period of) time t and in the same context true. In mathematical notation, the Law of Non-Contradiction can be represented as:

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = +1 \quad (17)$$

Where: $\neg$ denotes logical negation, $\wedge$ denotes logical conjunction (AND). The expression $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$ (see equation 17) is stating that the negation of a contradiction is true, which is consistent with classical logic and represents the negation of a logical contradiction, but not the logical contradiction itself.

2.1.2. The Law of Contradiction

The Law of Contradiction is another fundamental principle that describes the relationship between something, denoted by X_{Rt} , and its own negation, denoted by $\neg X_{Rt}$, at the same (period of) time t and in the same context. In mathematical notation, the Law of Contradiction can be represented as:

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = +0 \quad (18)$$

Where: $\neg$ denotes logical negation, $\wedge$ denotes logical conjunction (AND).

2.2. Axioms

Axioms are invaluable in science and the deductive method, as they serve as foundational principles upon which the entire logical framework of a theory or system is built. Furthermore, axioms provide a starting point for deducing further conclusions and theorems. However, it is necessary that axioms are self-evident and true, allowing an extreme high degree of certainty in the deductive process. In toto, axioms can help us to ensure the logical consistency and coherence of a theory. Besides of all, axioms can be used to define the basic concepts and terms used within a particular field of study, enabling clear and precise communication. In principle, axioms might play a crucial role in shaping the rigor and reliability of scientific reasoning and deduction.

2.2.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis - The law of non-contradiction

In this context, we define axiom I mathematically in the positive as

$$+1 = +1 \quad (19)$$

or in the negative as

$$-1 = -1 \quad (20)$$

Historically, the earliest documented use of **the law of identity** can be found in Plato's dialogue Theaetetus

“... each of the two is different from the other and the same as itself ”

(see [Plato, 424 – 348 B.C.E.](#), p. 104)

However, Aristotle (384–322 B.C.E.), Plato's pupil and equally a very famous Greek philosopher, elaborated on the law of identity too. In *Metaphysica*, Aristotle wrote:

“... all things ... have some ... identity. ”

(see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaphysica*, Chapter IV, 999a, 25-30, p. 66)

For the sake of completeness, it should be noted at the outset that Aristotle himself preferred **the law of contradiction** and **the law of excluded middle** as examples of fundamental axioms. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that **lex identitatis** is an axiom too, which possess the potential to serve as the most basic and equally the most simple axiom of science but has been treated by Aristotle in an inadequate manner without having any clear and determined meaning for Aristotle himself. Nonetheless, something which is really just itself is equally different from everything else. In point of fact, is such an equivalence ([Degen, 1741](#)) which everything has to itself inherent or must the same be constructed by human mind

and consciousness. Can and how can something be **identical with itself** (Förster and Melamed, 2012; Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1812; Koch, 1999; Newstadt, 2015b) and in the same respect different from itself? An increasingly popular view on identity is the one advocated by Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1716):

**“Chaque chose est ce qu’elle est. Et dans autant d’exemples qu’on voudra
A est A,
B est B. ”**
(Leibniz, 1765, p. 327)

or **A = A, B = B** or **+1 = +1**. In other words, a thing is what it is (Leibniz, 1765, p. 327). Leibniz’ **principium identitatis indiscernibilium** (p.i.i.), the principle of the indistinguishable, occupies a central position in Leibniz’ logic and metaphysics and was formulated by Leibniz himself in different ways in different passages (1663, 1686, 1704, 1715/16). All in all, Leibniz writes:

“C’est
le principe des indiscernables,
en vertu duquel
il ne saurait exister dans la nature deux êtres identiques.
...
Il n’y a point deux individus indiscernables. ”
(see Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm, 1886, p. 45)

Exactly in complete compliance with Leibniz, Johann Gottlieb Fichte (1762 - 1814) elaborates on this subject as follows:

**“Each thing is what it is ;
it has those realities which are posited when it is posited,
(A = A.) ”**
(Fichte, 1889)

Hegel preferred to reformulate an own version of Leibniz principium identitatis indiscernibilium in his own way by writing that “All things are different, or: there are no two things like each other. ”(see Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 422). Much of the debate about identity is still a matter of controversy. This issue has attracted the attention of many authors and has been discussed by Hegel too. In this context, it is worth to consider Hegel’s radical position on identity.

“The other expression of the law of identity: A cannot at the same time be A and not-A, has a negative form; it is called the law of contradiction. ”

(Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 416)

We may, usefully (see Barukčić, 2019), state Russell’s position with respect to the identity law as mentioned in his book ‘The problems of philosophy ’ (see Russell, 1912). In particular, according to Russell,

“...principles have been singled out by tradition under the name of ‘Laws of Thought.’ They are as follows:

(1) **The law of identity:** ‘Whatever is, is.

(2) **The law of contradiction:** ‘Nothing can both be and not be.’

(3) **The law of excluded middle:** ‘Everything must either be or not be.’

These three laws are samples of self-evident logical principles, but are not really more fundamental or more self-evident than various other similar principles: for instance, the one we considered just now, which states that what follows from a true premise is true. The name ‘laws of thought’ is also misleading, for what is important is not the fact that we think in accordance with these laws, but the fact that **things behave in accordance with them;** ”

(see Russell, 1912, p. 113)

Russell’s critique, that we tend too much to focus only on the formal aspects of the ‘Laws of Thoughts’ with the consequence that “... we think in accordance with these laws” (see Russell, 1912, p. 113) is justified. Judged solely in terms of this aspect, it is of course necessary to think in accordance with the ‘Laws of Thoughts’. But this is not the only aspect of the ‘Laws of Thoughts’. The other and may be much more important aspect of these ‘Laws of Thoughts’ is the fact that quantum mechanical objects or that “... things behave in accordance with them” (see Russell, 1912, p. 113).

2.2.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis - The law of contradiction

In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, defined in the positive as

$$+0 = +1 \quad (21)$$

or in the negative as

$$-0 = -1 \quad (22)$$

is of no minor importance, too.

In philosophy, **the principle of explosion** or the principle of Pseudo-Scotus (Latin: **ex contradictione (sequitur) quodlibet**) demand us to accept that from falsehood or from a contradiction, any statement can be proven or anything may follow. However, scientist inevitably have false beliefs and make mistakes. In order to prevent us from falling into logical inconsistency or logical absurdity, it is necessary to possess the possibility to start a reasoning with a contradiction too. However and in contrast to the way of reasoning with inconsistent premises as proposed by para-consistent logic (see [Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#); [da Costa, 1974, 1958](#); [Priest, 1998](#); [Priest et al., 2018](#); [Quesada, 1977](#)), in the absence of technical and other errors of reasoning, the contradiction itself need to be preserved. In other words, **from a contradiction does not anything follows but a very concrete contradiction itself**. In addition to the above, from the point of view of mathematics, axiom II is equally the most simple mathematical expression and formulation of a contradiction. Today, a lot of ‘secured’ mathematical knowledge and rules differ too generously from real world processes, and the question may be asked whether mathematical truths can be treated as absolute truths at all. Many of the basic principle of today’s mathematics allow every single author defining the real world events and processes et cetera in a way as everyone likes it for himself. Consequentially, a resulting dogmatic epistemological subjectivism and at the end agnosticism too, might be one of the results. In the long term, however, history has taught us time and time again that objective reality has the potential to correct wrong human thinking slowly but surely, and many more than this. Objective reality has demonstrably corrected wrong human thinking again and again in the past. Despite all the adversities, it is necessary and crucial to consider that a self-identical as the opposite of itself is no longer only self-identity but a difference of itself from itself within itself. In other words, in opposition, a self-identical is able to return into simple unity with itself with the consequence that even as a self-identical the same self-identical is inherently self-contradictory. A question of fundamental theoretical importance is, however, why should something be itself and at the same time the other of itself, the opposite of itself, not itself? Is something like this even possible at all and if so, why and how? These and similar questions have occupied many thinkers, including Hegel.

“Something is therefore
alive only in so far as it contains contradiction within it,
and moreover is this power to
hold and endure the contradiction within it. ”

(see [Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991](#), p. 440)

However, as directed against identity, contradiction itself is also at the same time a source of self-changes out of itself of a self-identical.

“... contradiction
is the root of all movement and vitality;
it is only in so far as something has a contradiction within it
that it moves, has an urge and activity. ”

(see [Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991](#), p. 439)

The further advance of science will throw any contribution to scientific progress of each of us back into scientific insignificance, as long as principium contradictionis is not given enough and the right attention. **The contradiction is existing objectively and real** (see [Barukčić, 2020](#)) and is the heartbeat of every self-identical. We have reason to be delighted by the fact that very different aspects of principium contradictionis have been examined since centuries from different angles by various authors. Aristotle's understanding of principium contradictionis is viewed by the following statement.

“... the same ... cannot at the same time belong and not belong to the same
... in the same respect ... This, then, is
the most certain of all principles ”

(see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph.*, IV, 3, 1005b, 16–22)

Principium contradictionis or axiom II has many facets. As long as we follow Leibniz in this regard, we should consider that “**Le principe de contradiction est en general ...**” ([Leibniz, 1765](#), p. 327). Scientist inevitably have false beliefs and make mistakes. In order to prevent scientific results from falling into logical inconsistency or logical absurdity, it is necessary to possess among other the methodological possibility to start a reasoning with a (logical) contradiction too. However and in contrast to the way of reasoning with inconsistent premises as proposed by para-consistent ([Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#); [da Costa, 1974, 1958](#); [Priest, 1998](#); [Priest et al., 1989](#); [Quesada, 1977](#)) and other logic, in the absence of technical and other errors of reasoning, the contradiction itself need to be preserved. In other words, **from a contradiction does not anything follows but the contradiction itself**, while the theoretical question is indeed justified “What is so Bad about Contradictions?” ([Priest, 1998](#)). Historically, **the principle of (deductive) explosion** ([Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#); [Priest, 1998](#); [Priest et al., 1989](#)), attributed to the 12th-century French philosopher William of Soissons, demand us to accept that anything, including its own negation, can be proven or can be inferred from a contradiction. In short, according to **ex falso sequitur quodlibet**, a (logical) contradiction implies anything. Respecting the principle of explosion, the existence of a contradiction (or the existence of logical inconsistency) in a scientific theorem, rule et cetera is disastrous. However, the historical development of science shows that scientist inevitably revise the theories, false positions and claims are identified once and again, and we all make different kind of mistakes. In order to avert disproportionately great damage to science and to prevent reducing science into pure subjective belief, a negation of the principle of explosion is required. Nonetheless, a justified negation of the **ex contradictione quodlibet principle** ([Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#)) does not imply the correctness of para consistent logic ([Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#); [da Costa, 1974, 1958](#); [Priest, 1998](#); [Priest et al., 1989](#); [Quesada, 1977](#)) as such as advocated especially by the Peruvian philosopher Francisco Miró Quesada ([Quesada, 1977](#)) and other ([Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#); [da Costa, 1974, 1958](#); [Priest, 1998](#); [Priest et al., 1989](#)). In general, scientific theories appear to progress from lower and simpler to higher and more complex levels. However, high level theories cannot be taken for granted because high level theories are grounded on a lot of assumptions, definitions and other procedures and may rest upon too much erroneous stuff even if still not identified. Therefore, it should be considered to check at lower at simpler levels like with like.

2.2.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis - The unity and the struggle between identity and contradiction

The process of (logical) negation is also an expression of the resolution of the conflict between identity and contradiction and mathematically defined in the positive as

$$+\neg(+0) \times +0 = +1 \quad (23)$$

and in the negative as

$$-\neg(0) \times 0 = -1 \quad (24)$$

where $\neg$ denotes (logical (see [Boole, 1854](#)) or natural) negation (see [Ayer, 1952](#); [Förster and Melamed, 2012](#); [Hedwig, 1980](#); [Heinemann, Fritz H., 1943](#); [Horn, 1989, 2001](#); [Koch, 1999](#); [Kunen, 1987](#); [Newstadt, 2015a](#); [Royce, 1917](#); [Speranza and Horn, 2010](#); [Wedin, 1990](#)). In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. Results

3.1. Conjunction and multiplication

Theorem 1 (Conjunction and multiplication are identical).

The logical operation of conjunction, denoted by $\wedge$, is identical to the algebraic operation of multiplication, denoted by $\cdot$.

Proof by direct proof. Let us consider the logical conjunction operation $\wedge$. It is

$$X_{Rt} \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}) = X_{Rt} \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}) \quad (\text{Starting Point})$$

As next, we assume that the logical conjunction operation $\wedge$ and the algebraic multiplication operation $\cdot$ are identical. In this case, we obtain:

$$X_{Rt} \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}) = X_{Rt} \cdot \neg(X_{Rt}) \quad (\text{Assumption})$$

This expression represents the logical AND operation ($\wedge$) between X_{Rt} and its negation ($\neg(X_{Rt})$). The algebraic multiplication ($\cdot$) represents the product of X_{Rt} and its negation. Now, we insert specific values into the equation and examine where it leads:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{Rt} \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}) &= X_{Rt} \cdot \neg(X_{Rt}) && (25) \\ \text{True} \wedge \neg(\text{True}) &= \text{True} \cdot \neg(\text{True}) && (\text{Assuming } X_{Rt} \text{ is true}) \\ \text{True} \wedge \text{False} &= \text{True} \cdot \text{False} && (\text{Negation of True is False}) \\ \text{False} &= \text{True} \cdot \text{False} && (\text{True AND False is False}) \end{aligned}$$

As next, we insert specific values into the equation while (true = +1) and (false = +0) and examine where it leads:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{Rt} \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}) &= X_{Rt} \cdot \neg(X_{Rt}) && (26) \\ 1 \wedge \neg(1) &= 1 \cdot \neg(1) && (\text{Assuming } X_{Rt} \text{ is } 1) \\ 1 \wedge 0 &= 1 \cdot 0 && (\text{Negation of } 1 \text{ is } 0) \\ 0 &= 1 \cdot 0 && (1 \text{ AND } 0 \text{ is } 0) \\ 0 &= 0 && (1 \text{ AND } 0 \text{ is } 0) \\ +1 - 1 &= +1 - 1 && (+1 - 1 \text{ is } 0) \\ +1 &= +1 && (-1 \text{ is subtracted away}) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

As we can see, when we insert specific values into the equation, both sides lead to the same result. This shows that the logical operation $\wedge$ (conjunction) is identical to the algebraic operation of multiplication, where True corresponds to 1 and False corresponds to 0.

$$\therefore X_{Rt} \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}) \text{ is identical to } X_{Rt} \cdot \neg(X_{Rt}). \quad (28)$$

□

3.2. The law of identity

The Law of Identity is one of the fundamental principles of classical logic. It states that each thing is the same with itself and different from another. In other words, it asserts that every object or entity is identical to itself. This principle can be expressed in a mathematical context as well. The Identity Law (or Law of Non-Contradiction) explicitly focuses on the negation of contradiction. However, if something is identical to itself, is there no contradiction within this identity? The equation $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$ represents a logical identity or a tautology in classical logic. A tautology is a statement that is always true, regardless of the truth values of its constituent variables. In this case, it asserts that the negation of the conjunction (AND) between a proposition (X_{Rt}) and its negation $\neg(X_{Rt})$ is always equal to 1 (true). This tautology is a fundamental principle in classical logic and is often used as the Law of Non-Contradiction. The equation $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$ on the left side evaluates to 1 (true). The equation $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$ does not represent a contradiction; rather, it asserts an identity or tautology. In this equation, it is stating that the negation of the conjunction (AND) between a proposition (X_{Rt}) and its negation $\neg(X_{Rt})$ is always equal to 1 (true). There is no contradiction in this identity; it affirms that a logical contradiction (P and not P) is always false, which is consistent with the principle of non-contradiction. The equation $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$ represents an identity and not a contradiction. The equation $1 = 1$ is indeed a mathematical expression of the Law of Identity. In mathematics, this equation means that the number 1 is equal to itself. This is a tautological statement and is always true by definition. It serves as a basic example of the Law of Identity, which applies not only to numbers but to any object, concept, or entity in classical logic and mathematics. So, in summary, the Law of Identity asserts that everything is identical to itself, and the equation $1 = 1$ is a mathematical expression of this principle, signifying that the number 1 is identical to itself.

Theorem 2 (The identity law).

We aim to prove that $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$ is identical with the identity law $1 = 1$.

Proof by direct proof. We apply the relationship between contradictory statements. It is

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) \quad (\text{Assumption})$$

As next, we proceed to break down the expression $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$ using De Morgan's Law (see [De Morgan, 1847](#), p. 118), which states that $\neg(A \wedge B)$ is equivalent to $(\neg A \vee \neg B)$. Applying De Morgan's Law:

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) \equiv (\neg(X_{Rt}) \vee (X_{Rt})) \quad (\text{De Morgan's Law})$$

Since $(\neg(X_{Rt}) \vee (X_{Rt})) = +1$ is a tautology (a statement that is always true, like $1 = 1$), we can replace $(\neg(X_{Rt}) \vee (X_{Rt}))$ with 1, as it represents a logical truism. We obtain,

$$\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) \equiv 1 \quad (\text{Tautology})$$

In other words, $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$ simplifies to 1. It is,

$$1 = 1 \quad (\text{Identity Law})$$

Hence, we have formally proven that $\neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$ is identical with the identity law.

$$\therefore \neg((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1 \text{ is identical with } 1 = 1. \quad (29)$$

□

3.3. The Law of Contradiction

Aristotle's discussions on the Law of Contradiction can be found in Book IV of *Metaphysics* (see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 3 1005b19–20*) too. Aristotle's writings are philosophical rather than mathematical in nature. The Law of Contradiction, as expressed by Aristotle, is a fundamental principle of classical logic, and its exposition is primarily in a philosophical context. Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction is a principle that highlights the logical relationship between contradictory states, statements, propositions et cetera. The Law of Contradiction asserts that two contradictory states, events, statements or propositions cannot both be true at the same time and in the same sense. In other words, the Law of Contradiction states that if one statement is true, the contradictory statement must be false. Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction emphasizes the logical incompatibility of contradictory claims. Historically, especially Scholasticism, which was the dominant intellectual movement in medieval Europe, heavily relied on the works of Aristotle and his logical principles. Scholastic philosophers, such as Thomas Aquinas (1225-1274), Albertus Magnus (c. 1193-1280), and Duns Scotus (c. 1266-1308), among others, incorporated Aristotle's logic and the Law of Contradiction into their philosophical writings.

Theorem 3 (The Law of Contradiction).

We aim to prove that $0 = 1$ is identical to $((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$.

Proof by direct proof. Now, let's consider the known expression $((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$ in more detail. It is claimed that

$$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1 \quad \text{(Starting Point)}$$

This expression represents the logical AND ($\wedge$) operation between X_{Rt} and its negation $\neg(X_{Rt})$. The logical AND operation yields 1 if and only if both operands are true. In this context, X_{Rt} represents a logical statement, and $\neg(X_{Rt})$ represents the negation of that statement.

Now, we insert specific values into the equation and examine where it leads:

$$\begin{aligned} ((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) &= 1 && (30) \\ (\text{True} \wedge \neg(\text{True})) &= 1 && \text{(Assuming } X_{Rt} \text{ is true)} \\ (\text{True} \wedge \text{False}) &= 1 && \text{(Negation of True is False)} \\ \text{False} &= 1 && \text{(True AND False is False)} \end{aligned}$$

As we can see, when we insert specific values into the equation, it leads to a contradiction ($0 = 1$). This shows that the initial assumption $0 = 1$ is indeed identical to $((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1$. The expression

$((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt}))$ essentially means that we have a logical contradiction. Thus far, there are conditions where something cannot be both true and false simultaneously, at the same (period of) time t .

$$\therefore ((X_{Rt}) \wedge \neg(X_{Rt})) = 1 \text{ is identical with } 0 = 1. \quad (31)$$

□

3.4. The Contradiction is existing objectively and real

Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction remains a fundamental principle in classical bivalent logic and is widely accepted as a cornerstone of rational reasoning. However, logical, philosophical and physical inquiry often involves questioning and refining even the most foundational principles of science. In view systems, contradictions can be accepted simultaneously. Therefore, the question arises, is the Law of Contradiction more or less context-dependent too?

As we know, one of the fundamental principles of the Special (see [Einstein, 1905](#)) Theory of Relativity is that the laws of physics are the same for all observers who are in inertial (non-accelerating) motion relative to each other. The proper quantities like proper time, denoted by t_0 , proper length, denoted by l_0 , and proper mass, denoted by m_0 , which are measured in special relativity by the co-moving (or internal) observer are of importance, because the same provide a consistent and observer-independent way to describe physical phenomena, even when observers are in relative motion.

Definitions from the point of view of a co-moving observer 0 In the context of the Special Theory of Relativity, a co-moving observer, denoted as 0, is an observer who is moving along with a particular object or reference frame, such that the relative velocity, denoted as v , with respect to that object or frame is zero. In other words, a co-moving observer is at rest relative to the object or reference frame he is observing. Thus far let:

c_0 denote the speed of light in vacuum from the point of view of a co-moving observer,

t_0 denote the time from the point of view of a co-moving observer ,

$$t_0 = t_R \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)},$$

s_0 denote the length of a path of a falling steel ball from the point of view of a co-moving observer,

$$s_0 = c_0 \times t_0,$$

v denote the relative velocity between a co-moving (internal) and a stationary (external) observer.

Definitions from the point of view of a stationary observer R

Let:

c_R denote the speed of light in vacuum from the point of view of a stationary observer,

t_R denote the time from the point of view of a stationary observer ,

$$t_R = \frac{t_0}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}},$$

s_R denote the length of a path of a falling steel ball from the point of view of a stationary observer,

$$s_R = c_R \times t_R,$$

v denote the relative velocity between a co-moving (internal) and a stationary (external) observer.

Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction is treated as a fundamental principle of classical logic, asserting that contradictory events, properties, statements et cetera cannot both be true simultaneously. The following theorem is based on the assumption that Aristotle's conception of the law of contradiction is universally valid, **contradictions do not exist**, neither in classical logic nor in special relativity theory nor somewhere else. In the following, we assume that both observers, the co-moving observer 0 and the stationary observer R, will measure the same length of the path, denoted as s_0 and s_R , of a steel ball falling perpendicular to the Earth's centre. If we take Aristotle's stance on the Law of Contradiction literally, then we obtain:

“... it is impossible
for the path of the same falling steel ball
at the same time
to have the same length
and
not to have the same length
... this is the most indisputable of all principles.”
(In accordance with [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E.](#), *Metaph IV 4 1008b8–10* (pdf p. 83/340))

Theorem 4 (Aristotle's Understanding of the Law of Contradiction is refuted).

Contradictions do exist objectively and real (see also [Barukčić, 2019](#)).

Proof by direct proof. In the following, we accept Aristotle's understanding of the law of contradiction as correct. Therefore, we start with the assumption that $s_0 = s_R$. In other words, there is no difference in the length of the same path as measured at the same time by the co-moving observer 0 compared to the measurement of the length of the same path at the same time by the stationary observer R. It is

$$s_0 = s_R \quad (32)$$

Now, rearrange this equation:

$$s_0 = c_0 \times t_0 = c_R \times t_R = s_R \quad (33)$$

Simplify the equation:

$$c_0 \times t_0 = c_R \times t_R \quad (34)$$

Now, consider that

$$t_R = \frac{t_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (35)$$

Substitute t_R back into the equation:

$$c_0 \times t_0 = c_R \times \left(\frac{t_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \right)$$

Consider that $c_0 = c_R$ since we're dealing with the speed of light under conditions of special theory of relativity. We can simplify further:

$$t_0 = t_0 \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (36)$$

Divide both sides of the equation by t_0 and obtain:

$$1 = 1 \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (37)$$

Now, let's square both sides:

$$1^2 = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \right)^2 \quad (38)$$

Simplify the right side:

$$1 = 1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2} \quad (39)$$

Now, isolate v^2 :

$$v^2 = c^2 - c^2 \cdot 1 \quad (40)$$

Simplify further:

$$v^2 = c^2 - c^2 \quad (41)$$

And finally:

$$v^2 = 0 \quad (42)$$

Given: $v = 1$ km/second. We have reached a contradiction:

$$+1 = +0 \quad (43)$$

□

A logical contradiction has been derived from Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity. Does this contradiction arise from a flaw in the theory itself and not from other sources? We should not simply disregard the fact that Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity has been extensively tested and confirmed through experiments and observations. Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity accurately describes the behaviour of objects at high speeds and has been a foundational theory in modern physics. Nowadays and at this point, it doesn't make any sense to contemplate the logical inconsistency of Einstein's theory of special relativity. However, we cannot simply disregard the fact either that we have a contradiction (see equation 43). So, where is the mistake, were there any technical errors in the argumentation? No, none to be found far and wide. So, where then is the mistake?

The contradiction in the proof provided just before arose from equation 32 where we accepted the general validity of Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction. Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction (see equation 32), which excludes any contradiction, leads itself straightforward into a contradiction (see equation 43). The value of such a principle does not become evident to me in any way as such. Equation 43 does not undermine the well-established principles of the theory of special relativity but has refuted Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction. A follower of Aristotle might feel compelled to point out that the apparent contradiction in the previous proof arises because it attempts to apply classical logic, based on Aristotle's understanding of the Law of Contradiction, to a physical theory designed for extreme conditions, where classical logic don't hold.

However, what is the value of any logic that is not in compliance with real-world situations? The previous proof highlights among other the importance of recognizing the limitations of any logical framework and to modify or to extend any logical framework if the same contradicts empirical evidence when confronted with objective reality. In scientific endeavours, experimental results and empirical observations ultimately might serve as the arbiter of the validity of any logical framework. If a logical system consistently fails to describe or predict real-world phenomena accurately, it may require revision or supplementation to remain relevant in the face of new discoveries, or it needs to be abandoned. In this sense, the value of any logic lies not only in its internal coherence, but also in its ability to model and explain the complexities of the world around us and of the world within us. Classical logic explains the most basic and equally the most simple laws of nature, and not only laws of thoughts.

3.5. Refutation of Aristotle's Principle of Explosion

The Principle of Explosion, also known as *ex falso quodlibet*, is a fundamental concept even in today classical logic. Its historical roots can be traced back to ancient Greek philosophers, particularly Aristotle, who is said to have laid the groundwork for formal logic. The claim that the Principle of Explosion, also known as *ex falso quodlibet* or *from contradiction, anything follows*, has been proven (see [Lewis and Langford, 1932](#)) by the 12th-century French philosopher William of Soissons appears to be not completely accurate. Even Thomas Aquinas, an influential medieval philosopher who discussed logical principles, did not introduce the Principle of Explosion. In brief, the Principle of Explosion asserts that from a contradiction, any conclusion can be validly inferred. In other words, starting with contradiction, any conclusion desire can be derived or contradictions are inherently false, allowing us to lead to any conclusion. In the pursuit of reaching only the correct conclusions and not just any arbitrary ones, scientist therefore maintained a significant distance from the Principle of Explosion and contradictions as such. As a consequence, a crucial epistemological corrective to promptly identify and rectify erroneous thinking has been systematically withheld from scientists for thousands of years. It is therefore not surprising at all that the Principle of Explosion has had far-reaching consequences for logical reasoning and the development of science as such. The introduction of the Principle of Explosion is attributed to Aristotle, who formalized many principles in his approach to logic, it doesn't matter whether right or wrong. Even today, a significant portion of scientific theoretical frameworks still relies on largely incorrect dogmas and beliefs put forth by Aristotle. Nonetheless, in the ongoing (re-) evolution and refinement of logical systems in the field of philosophy and formal logic, especially in para-consistent (see [Carnielli and Marcos, 2001](#); [da Costa, 1974, 1958](#); [Priest, 1998](#); [Priest et al., 2018](#); [Quesada, 1977](#)) or non-classical i.e. dialectical logics, Aristotle's Principle of Explosion and many other principles are questioned, modified or even abandoned in toto. Therefore, is Aristotle's Principle of Explosion correct at all and can this be proofed somehow? The refutation of the Principle of Explosion which follows starts with the assumption of a contradiction and demonstrates that this contradiction leads to another contradiction. So far, so good.

However, the experiment of starting with the contradiction $+0 = +1$ and then adding $+1$ to both sides is repeated infinitely many times, we will continue to get: $+1 = +2$ and not any result or any conclusion desired. In other words, the result will not change regardless of how many times the experiment before is repeated, the contradiction $+1 = +2$ itself is completely preserved. For this obvious reason, we have no other choice but to conclude that the Principle of Explosion is refuted in toto.

Theorem 5. *Refutation of the Principle of Explosion Claim: The Principle of Explosion is refuted.*

Proof. Let's begin by assuming a contradiction:

$$0 = 1 \tag{44}$$

Now, add 1 to both sides of the equation:

$$1 = 2 \tag{45}$$

We have derived another contradiction:

$$1 = 2 \quad (46)$$

This proof demonstrates that starting with a contradiction, we obtained another contradiction.

If we were to repeat this process infinitely, we would consistently arrive at the same contradictory result, rather than any desired conclusion. Thus, the Principle of Explosion, which suggests that from a contradiction, any statement can be derived, is refuted.

Hence, the claim is proven, and the Principle of Explosion is refuted. $\square$

The equation $+1 = +2$ is indeed a contradiction and is of course mathematically nonsensical. However, in mathematics and other sciences, it is important to identify and correct such errors as $+1 = +2$ in mathematical reasoning, since contradictions like this one indicate that something is fundamentally wrong with the underlying assumptions or logic being used. The Principle of Explosion (*ex falso quodlibet*) does not allow scientists in any way to even think about such a possibility. This is reminiscent of the medieval ban on opening the body of a deceased person and also to research the causes of his death. It is entirely conceivable that, over the course of millennia, scientists, especially in the realm of mathematics, were compelled to forgo crucial means of detecting and rectifying errors. In the realm of pure contemplation, it is within the realm of possibility that errors, particularly within the domain of mathematics, may have accrued over centuries. From this vantage point, we may glean a deeper understanding of Einstein's stance on mathematics.

**“I don’t
believe in
mathematics.”**

(Albert Einstein cited according to [Brian, 1996](#), p. 76)

Finally, it is high time to consign Aristotle's false, otherworldly, and individual-contemptuous principles to the scrapheap of scientific knowledge, where they should be permanently discarded. It is entirely conceivable that the refutation presented here of Aristotle's Principle of Explosion could, at the very least, cause significant discomfort to many adherents of Aristotle's Principle of Explosion. While the proof before refutes the Principle of Explosion (*ex falso quodlibet*), the same proof actually relies on a very subtle issue within classical logic, this could be only one of the counterarguments. A critic might perceive a fundamental issue on this point. It could cause considerable discomfort to many to commence an entire chain of argumentation with a contradiction. This is precisely prohibited by the Principle of Explosion. However, how are we supposed to verify the validity of this principle when we

are forbidden from examining its consequences? Aristotle's Principle of Explosion is a prime example of the logical fallacy of circular reasoning. It is only with the utmost effort that one can free himself from the logical and mental captivity of a logical fallacy, **the black hole of human reasoning**.

Example: Logical fallacy of circular reasoning.

The first premise: "We should never accept conclusions derived from contradictions."

The second premise: Why? Because the Principle of Explosion tells us that from a contradiction, anything follows.

Conclusion: Therefore, "We should never accept conclusions derived from contradictions."

In this example, the first premise asserts that we should not accept conclusions derived from contradictions. However, the second premise relies on the Principle of Explosion to justify this claim. This reasoning becomes circular because the Principle of Explosion itself is used to justify the claim that we shouldn't accept conclusions from contradictions.

In other words, the problem is not the initial assumption that $+0 = +1$, which is a contradiction, but the unroofed claim that any conclusion can be drawn from a such a contradiction (known as the Principle of Explosion). In point of fact, by starting with a contradiction and deriving another contradiction (e.g., $+1 = +2$), the contradiction itself is preserved. Thus far, in the absence of a (logical) negation or in the absence of other (technical) errors, from something absurd, something absurd follows. Again, contradictions in the absence of a (logical) negation and in the absence of other (technical) errors cannot be used to derive any contradiction or conclusions, but only to derive a very concrete contradiction.

4. Discussion

Historically, contradictions are many times viewed through the methodological lens of dialectical thinking, often associated with philosophers like Heraclitus, with the group of early Hellenistic philosophers (like Eubulides of Miletus, Diodorus Cronus, Philo the Logician), with Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, Karl Marx and other too. Heraclitus (about 500 B. C. E.), the ancient Greek philosopher known for his views on change and the nature of reality, had a complex view on contradictions. In contrast to Aristotle, Heraclitus believed in the unity of opposites, suggesting that contradictory elements were interconnected and part of a larger whole. Heraclitus's position on contradictions was deeply intertwined with his broader philosophy of change and unity. The doctrine of Heraclitus is "... all things are and are not ..." (Heraclitus, cited according to [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph IV 7 1012a 25](#) (pdf p. 99/340)). As an example:

"... it is impossible to step twice into the same river ... "

(Heraclitus, cited according to [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph IV 5 1010a 27–28](#) (pdf p. 93/340))

In contrast to Aristotle, Heraclitus saw contradictions as essential components of a dynamic and interconnected objective reality, where opposites played a fundamental role in the ongoing process of transformation and growth. Aristotle in his critique and attack on Heraclitus's philosophy, particularly on Heraclitus view on the nature of contradictory statements, implies that Heraclitus might not have fully grasped the implications of his own statement and wrote:

"... if we had questioned Heraclitus himself ... we might have forced him to confess that

opposite statements can never be true of the same subjects.

... without understanding what his statement involved ... what is said by him ...

the same thing can at one and the same time both be and not be. "

(see [Aristotle, 384-322 B.C.E., Metaph XI 5 1062a32–1062b2](#) (pdf p. 238/340))

The problem addressed here by Aristotle is just a trial to provide evidence of potentially inherent contradictions in Heraclitus's philosophy rather than analysing the relationship between opposites in an adequate and profound manner. Nonetheless, by critiquing Heraclitus's view on contradictory statements, Aristotle himself is highlighting, even if only superficially, the logical challenges which might arise from accepting the coexistence of opposite truths. However, even today, dialectics is itself characterized more or less by an interplay of opposites and is regarded as a mode of reasoning that seeks to understand objective reality as a dynamic process marked by contradictions and their resolutions. In the meantime, it was possible to provide objective evidence that **contradictions are existing objectively and real** (see [Barukčić, 2019](#)). In toto, contradictions need not be seen as problems to be

avoided, but as dynamic events, processes of nature et cetera that drive change, development and evolution forward. A contradiction arises at least under circumstances where there is an inherent tension or opposition between identical, which are different too. Nonetheless, contradictions are not merely negations of each other, but more or less interconnected with each other in a larger unity of opposites. Such a unity of opposites encompasses both aspects of the contradiction and might lead to a higher level of development. The view lines before underscores the importance of recognizing and engaging with contradictions as driving forces of change and growth in both the natural world and human societies. This insight invites us to view contradictions not as obstacles to be avoided but as opportunities for development and transformation. In other words, when there is a contradiction within something, it is compelled to move and change. This movement is driven by the inherent struggle between opposites, seeking for a resolution or for a new equilibrium. At the end, continuous change and adaptation is a possible result. In the process of resolving contradictions, progress and development occurs, while vitality and growth might be seen as outcomes of resolving contradictions. However, circumstances devoid of contradictions may lead to inertia and stagnation. Without opposites or opposition, there may be little incentive for change or improvement. In this context, static and one-sided thinking might seek to eliminate contradictions altogether. However, such attempts may suppress creativity and hinder progress. The complexity of objective reality, even human life itself, is filled with contradictions. A more systematic approach to contradictions might provide us with a more realistic and dynamic framework for understanding objective reality. In this context, Hegel perceptively notes the following insights, capturing the essence of the matter with a profound and poetic resonance. His observations resonate with a timeless wisdom that transcends the confines of mere words, inviting us to contemplate the depths of his thought and the enduring relevance of his understanding of contradiction.

“... contradiction
is the root of all movement and vitality;
it is only in so far as something has a contradiction within it
that it moves, has an urge and activity. ”

(see [Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991](#), p. 439)

5. Conclusion

The unity of nature is the foundation of the unity of science. As demonstrated beyond any reasonable doubt, there are circumstances where Aristotle’s Understanding of the Law of Contradiction breaks down.

‘Aristotle’s Understanding of the Law of Contradiction is not generally valid and therefore refuted. ’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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Associated Data

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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